

A Comparison of Traditional and Digital Methods for Stemmatic Analysis of the Chronicle of Matthew of Edessa

The purpose of the talk is presenting the stemmatic analysis of the manuscript tradition of the Chronicle of Matthew of Edessa, a 12th century Armenian language historical text, in preparation for a digital critical edition to appear in 2019. Around 40 known manuscripts, that contain the full text of the Chronicle or some portions of it, were copied from the end of 16th till the 19th centuries.

Currently we have 30 transcribed manuscripts that are encoded with [TEI](#) XML tags. They were collated with a “software for collating textual sources” called [CollateX](#). The next stage of digital critical edition is stemmatic analysis (Robinson 420–21). We have decided to do the stemmatic analysis in both traditional and digital ways and to compare the results. One of the authors is responsible for the stemmatic analysis in the traditional way, and the other author is using the digital approach. In this paper, we will detail the ideas behind both approaches and some specifics of our current work. The final results of the stemmatic analysis, along with some reflections on the relative merits of the methods, will be presented during the conference.

Traditional approach

In order to form a stemma in traditional way within the frames of this investigation, we have carried out a sourceological analysis of 28 manuscripts of the Chronicle of Matteos Urhayeci (Matthew of Edessa). The analysis of the manuscripts has been carried out in two stages in each of which we were accordingly led by the archeological description of the manuscripts and approaches to textological analyses. For this the methods are used in this paper can be divided into two groups:

- 1) Archeological (the analysis of the external form of witnesses). The description of the composition of manuscripts makes it possible to identify groups of related manuscripts. The relationship of manuscripts is indicated by common gaps in their texts and common contents, which means the presence in the different manuscripts of the same works located before and after the Chronicle. It is worth mentioning that for the initial grouping of the manuscripts we have chosen not only the thematic divisions, but also chronological boundaries of the texts, as far as both lets us outline the initial groupings of the manuscripts of Chronicle from the very

beginning. Manuscripts of Chronicle were collected into three groups. The classification is based on the end date (year), the events of which are described in the texts of Chronicle.

Thus, archaeological description shows:

a) The text of the Chronicle ends in the entry for 611 (1162/3) in one group (from now group A), in the middle of the entry for 546 (1097/8) in manuscripts of the second group (from now group B), in the entry for 560 (1111/2) in manuscripts of the third group (from now group C).

b) Matteos Urhayeci's Chronicle basically follows the work "On Wine and Drunkenness" and precedes Tovma Metsopetsi's "History Tamur and His Successors" in manuscripts of group B. Chronicle basically follows Mesrop Vayocdzortsi's "History of Nerses the Great" in manuscripts of group A. The oldest manuscript of group C also follows Mesrop Vayotsdzortsi's "History of Nerses the Great", which may indicate the relationship of it with group A.

c) The texts of manuscript group B is basically organized by highlighted headings, ornamental initial letters. Some manuscripts of this group also have margin ornaments and the same margin miniatures. Compared with group B, graphic design of the Chronicle's texts in group A is too simple. It is limited only with highlighted initial letters. (Just few manuscripts have highlighted initial sentences, numbers and symbols in the margins). The texts of manuscripts of group C have not any graphic design.

The results of archaeological description give a real, but only the initial and general grouping of manuscripts. For having an idea of relationships between manuscripts, branches and groups, it is necessary to use additional possibilities, which gives a comparative textual analysis.

2) Comparative-textological. It is based on close analysis of the similarities and differences existing between witnesses. This method has used:

a) To restore the relationship between witnesses.

b) To reveal the characteristics of non-surviving archetypes and exemplars.

Thus, comparing the texts of the Chronicle, were revealed the differences and similarities between them. Analysis of the variant readings and their classification made it possible to reveal the texts with common differences and similarities, by which the manuscripts were collected into groups and branches and revealed the relationship between the manuscripts. Our analysis is based on the assumption that more common variant readings and textual features between the witnesses, closer they are, and vice versa, then less similarities they have, the more independent they are. The analysis was carried out according to the 1) content, 2) structural and 3) textual peculiarities: a) additions, b) omissions, c) deletions, d) mistakes, e) glosses, f)

margin notes and colophons, etc. As this work is not linguistic, it does not consider a number of variant readings, the analysis of which would have a value mainly for the history of the language, such as differences in spelling of words, proper names, etc.

Comparing the texts of the Chronicle we revealed the all variant readings and textual peculiarities between the manuscripts. Then, when all variant readings and textual peculiarities were revealed and classified, we described textual peculiarities group by group and passed to the definition relations between manuscripts and building the stemma (see fig. 1).

Digital approach

Creating a stemma of a text using the most common digital approach, which employs phylogenetic analysis algorithms, can be broken down into two stages. The first stage is to create the phylogenetic tree of the manuscripts and the second is to use the tree, along with any other evidence available, to create the real stemma. In this research we have compared the results of traditional stemmatic analysis and phylogenetic analysis.

It is important to define the relationships between the variations before starting the stemmatic analysis, that's why, first of all, we used "Relationship mapper" tool in [stemmaweb](#) (Andrews and Macé) to verify the variations existing in the manuscripts.

Phylogenetic methods, that can be used for stemmatic analysis, were taken from evolutionary biology. Phylogenetics analyzes the changes that took place during evolution in DNA sequence of different groups of organisms. When evolutionary biologists find similar sequence in DNA of organisms of different groups, they conclude that these different groups originated from the same ancestor (Orr). The same principle can be used in stemmatic analysis.

There are some different methods taken from evolutionary biology to apply in stemmatic analysis, such as neighbour joining, maximum parsimony and there are some methods created exactly for stemmatic analysis, such as the RHM method (Roos et al.).

We did not manage to finish stemmatic analysis before the conference. We will, thus, present the results we got so far. Our phylogenetic analysis is based on eleven sections (of 140) of the text of the Chronicle and only after correction (p.c.) layer. We have used maximum parsimony (Fig. 2) and RHM (Fig. 3) methods and are planning to use neighbour joining method. The maximum parsimony method is based on grouping and subgrouping witnesses according to the differences between them (CHRISTOPHER J. HOWE et al. 54). The principle of RHM method is calculating the comprehensive amount of the differences between the

Fig. 2, Parsimony tree

Fig. 3, RHM tree

Fig. 4, The parsimony tree vs traditional stemma.

Fig. 5, The RHM tree vs traditional stemma.

Fig. 6, Parsimony tree vs RHM tree.

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